

A Rapid Assessment of Malnutrition in School-Going Children (6-13 Years) in a Rural District of Assam

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ABSTRACT

The Government of India started a “Call to Action” for improving Maternal and Child Survival and aligning health indicators with the Sustainable Goals. In this endeavour, 189 high-priority districts were identified, of which six were identified in Assam. Ayushman Arogya Mandir or Health Wellness Centres were initiated, and a cadre of Community Health Officers was created to operate them. This study was conducted as a part of Rastriya Bal Suraksha Karyakram. A rapid assessment of socio-demographic profile and malnutrition status was done on 505 school children using a structured questionnaire in six government-aided schools. Malnutrition was found to be higher than the state average. Nutritional status was assessed as normal nutrition (12.9%), moderate nutrition (23.8%) and under-nutrition (63.4%). Drinking water sources were unsafe, like ponds, open wells or hand pumps. Children belonged to low socioeconomic backgrounds. Consumption of low-cost, unhealthy sugary beverages and empty-calorie diets was high in the study population. The incidence of caries in teeth was found. Caries teeth could be possible confounders/effect modifiers of malnutrition. Findings create important hypotheses that can form a basis for further research.

Keywords:

Malnutrition, IAP Growth Chart, Dental Caries, Confounders, Cariogenic food..

Introduction

Children’s nutrition is an important indicator of their health and survival. Despite global efforts to improve the nutritional status of children aged 6 to 13 years, under-nutrition remains a major health problem in India. There are three main methods of measuring nutrition: dietary, biochemical, and anthropometric.

Under-nutrition encompasses a range of conditions, ranging from mild under-nutrition with poor growth to severe under-nutrition with high mortality, such as malignant dystrophy and marasmus. Children’s food is associated with poverty, under-nutrition and disease. These factors relate to general living standards and access to basic needs such as food, shelter and healthcare. [1] Stunting, defined as average height for age minus two standard deviations,

indicates under-nutrition. Wasting is defined by height and weight and represents severe malnutrition. Each type of eating disorder has different origins and hence requires different treatment and intervention. Undernourished children have a higher risk of death, but they are also at greater risk. Undernutrition is related to food intake rather than inadequate nutrition. For example, moderate weight loss is associated with 30–148 deaths per 1000 children per year; moderate weight loss is associated with 73–187 deaths per 1000 children per year [2].

Under-nutrition among primary school children is a major problem, identified by the World Health Organisation (WHO) as the leading cause of undernutrition and causes the deaths of millions of children worldwide each year. It is estimated that 50% of students drop out of primary school due to poor

health, child labour and lack of motivation, as well as child under-nutrition. Under-nutrition in children can lead to poor growth, poor organ production and function, poor physical performance, and poor neurological and cognitive function. It also prevents children from reaching their physical and mental potential. In India, approximately 70% of the population earns their living from agriculture. The health and cleanliness of society directly affect people's health. The Global Health Index 2023 shows that India is among the countries in the world with the highest rate of stunting in children at 18.7%, the rate of stunting in children at 35.5%, and under-nutrition at 16.6%. More than 40 per cent of young people receive less food than they should, and almost a third of Indians are considered malnourished. In the 2024 Global Hunger Index, India ranks 105th out of the 127 countries with sufficient data to calculate 2024 GHI scores. With a score of 27.3 in the 2024 Global Hunger Index, India has a level of hunger that is serious. [3]

Community nutrition studies in children are needed to prevent under-nutrition and to determine the prevalence of under-nutrition and related problems in India. According to India's National Nutrition Strategy, proper nutrition has been ensured for every child in India, especially the disadvantaged groups in society. In 2004, improving the maternal, newborn and child health indicators was targeted in India, and hence the National Rural Health Mission was envisaged and launched. The Urban Health Sub-Mission component was included in it and was called the National Health Mission. RMNCH+A strategy is an innovative approach and also a management reform, like the selection of high-priority districts with identified poor-performing areas that require high-impact intervention. High-priority districts were selected based on HMIS indicators, as per states like Assam, from the Annual Health Survey 2012-13 as the base year. Karimganj (now renamed as Sribhumi) is one such high-priority district. Development partners were selected for each state and district to provide technical support to roll out high-impact interventions. "A CALL TO ACTION" for committing to Child Survival was jointly

launched in June 2012 by the Government of India, Ethiopia and the USA in partnership with UNICEF. The call seeks to mobilise the leadership and commitment of the respective governments, civil societies, academia, and private sector organisations for renewing their collective promise towards the cause of 'Child Survival'.

Objectives of the Study

1. Identify sociodemographic factors that may influence their nutritional status.
2. Estimate the prevalence of undernutrition among the children aged 6–13 years.
3. To study their dietary habits, oral health status and hygiene behaviour likely associated with possible health risks.
4. Develop appropriate strategies to prevent and control undernutrition.

Methodology

The study was done on 6-13-year-old children attending primary and upper-primary sections in government-aided schools located in a rural district of Assam. The study is descriptive, school-based, and cross-sectional. It received the ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethics Committee of NSHM Knowledge Campus, Kolkata vide NSHMKOL/IEC/3/2024/PR-14 dated 27.02.2024. The duration of the study was from February 2024 to May 2024. A total of six schools were identified in the study area, out of which three were government schools and the remaining three were privately owned. Parents or guardians of 505 children (6-13 years) were invited to participate in a scheduled clinical assessment within the school premises. Written informed consent was obtained from parents and children participating in this study.

Inclusion Criteria: Children whose parents were willing to allow their children to participate and sign the informed consent form, and children (male and female) who were in the age group 6-13 years. **Exclusion criteria-** Children previously diagnosed with associated health conditions (e.g., Down syndrome, asthma, or any other chronic

disease etc.) or if parents or guardians did not allow their children to take part in this study. The sample size estimation did not apply to this study, as all eligible children studying in the selected schools located in the study area were subjected to this study. Information was collected using a survey proforma comprising a closed-ended questionnaire. Clinical examination was done for each student. Children were examined for oral hygiene status with the help of a tongue depressor, mouth mirror and gauge sponges. The questionnaire consisted of 5 sections, which dealt with the identification of socio-demographic details of the child's family, personal information related to his/her nutrition and hygiene behaviour, information about services received at school to improve their health and nutritional status, and a section on clinical and anthropometric assessments. A high-precision digital weighing machine & anthropometric rod were used for the measurement of weight and height of the study subjects. Data was filled in MS Excel and exported into SPSS.

Results and Findings

Table 1 describes the socio-demographic profile of study participants. Independent Variables identified in the study were mothers' education, family income, water and sanitation, family size, whereas dependent variables were age, dietary habits, nutritional status, gender, and IAP Growth chart.

In the study population, 50.3% were boys, and the remaining (49.7%) were girls. 39.8% children were in the age group of 6-9 years (Primary Class), and the rest (60.2%) were in the age group 10-13 years (Upper Primary Class). 9.3% mothers/primary caretakers were illiterate, 21.9% knew how to read and write, 53.2% had attained primary education, 12.07% had attained upper-primary education, and the remaining had passed their secondary exam or above qualifications. With regards to occupation, 7.9% parents/guardians were cultivators, 24.2% parents/guardians were daily wage earners (labourers, drivers), 20.6% parents/guardians were artisans, 3.4% parents/guardians were service holders, 18.8% parents/guardians

were businessmen, and the remaining 25.1% were self-employed.

Furthermore, in our study, the household income of family members per month showed that 16% households were earning a monthly income of less than 5000 INR, 80.1% had a monthly income in the range of 5000- 10000 INR and 3.9% households had an income of more than 10000 INR. The major source of drinking water was an uncovered well (65.1%), and only 1.8% had access to piped water or a deep tubewell (18.4%).

Assessment of nutritional status

“Malnutrition” is generally caused when a person's energy and intake of nutrients are deficient, excessive, or imbalanced over a significant period. Low weight compared to height is called wasting. If a child has low weight as compared to his age, the condition is referred to as stunting.

Children who weigh less than their age (low weight for age) are said to be underweight (WHO Fact Sheet, 2024). **Table 2** demonstrates the details about stunting and wasting in our study population. 269 children were found to have stunted growth, 276 children were found to have only wasting, and 320 children were found to have both stunting & wasting.

Nutritional Assessment was done using guidelines of the Indian Academy of Paediatrics (IAP) with their reference values for Height and Weight of 5- 18-year-old Indian boys and girls. Low risk was considered for children having either height or weight or both measured between the 10th and 25th percentiles. Ideal or appropriate nutritional status was considered for children with both height and weight measured between the 25th and 75th percentiles as per the IAP reference population. Under-nutrition was considered as having either weight or height or both less than the third percentile in respect to his or her age and sex as guided by IAP [4].

Out of 505 children, 65 children (12.9%) had normal nutrition, 120 children (23.8%) had moderate nutrition, and the remaining 320 children were found to be undernourished. Prevalence of under-nutrition was found to

be alarmingly high (63.4%) in the study population, as evident in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Nutritional Status (as per IAP Growth Chart).

Nutritional Assessment Outcomes

Data analysis was done using SPSS software. Chi-square was used to compare outcomes. There is no statistically significant difference across age categories, gender, income, family size and occupation (a two-sided probability of $P < 0.05$ is considered for testing significance). Significance was established only across one factor, namely, the education status of the caregiver, which was either the mother or the primary caretaker ($P < 0.0001$, Chi-square value was found to be 266.145), very similar to the findings in another study [5].

Oral Hygiene Status & Behavioural Practices

Oral examination confirmed that more than half of the study population (53.1%) had good oral health. The remaining population showed prevailing dental conditions (including toothache, sensitive tooth, caries and swollen gums). Out of the total study population (N=505 children), 237 children (46.9%) had problems with dental caries, 37.6% reported dental caries accompanied by toothache and 9.3% children were diagnosed with swollen/bleeding gums. The majority of the respondents had never visited the dentist in the last two years. 37 respondents (15.6%) claimed they had visited the dentist once in the last two years. 23 respondents (9.7%) claimed they have visited the dentist more than three times in the last two years. Regarding brushing habits, 34.6% brushed

once, while 65.4% brushed twice a day. The most preferred cleaning agent was toothpaste (62.2%), ash (37.4%) and powder/majan (0.4%). The prevalence of dental caries in children was found to be 37.6%.

Photo Plate 1. Swollen gums and Caries in a 10-year-old participant.

Photo Plate 2. Caries in an 11-year-old participant.

Pure drinking water is the basic need for good health. As discussed in **Table 1**, the majority didn't have access to safe and potable drinking water. A good source of drinking water can decrease the risk of tooth decay and gum disease. [6] Availability of portable water regularly helps to clean the mouth several times a day, washing away leftover food and residues that cavity-causing bacteria love to eat. Caries teeth could be possible confounders/effect modifiers of malnutrition. Findings create important hypotheses that can form a basis for further research.

Table 1. Distribution of the Study population as per sociodemographic Status

Socio-demographic characteristics (N=505)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Category in years		
6-9	201	39.8
10-13	304	60.2
Gender		
Boys	254	50.3
Girls	251	49.7
Education Status of Mother/Caretaker		
Illiterate	47	9.3
Can read and write without formal schooling	111	21.9
Primary	269	53.2
Secondary School	61	12.1
Higher Secondary and above	17	3.5
Occupation of Head of Family		
Agriculture	40	7.9
Daily wage earner (labourers, drivers)	122	24.2
Artisans	104	20.6
Businessmen	95	18.8
Service holders	17	3.4
Self employed	127	25.1
Family size		
4 members	121	23.9
≥ 5 members or above	384	76.1
Household family income in INR		
<5000	81	16.0
5000-10000	404	80.1
>10000	20	3.9
Source of drinking water		
Piped water	9	1.8
Covered well	2	0.4
Deep Tube well	93	18.4
Ponds	72	14.3
Uncovered well	329	65.1

Table 2. Stunting & Wasting in Primary and Upper-primary school children

Under-Nutrition (N=505)	Total number of children	Percentage (%)
Stunting	269	53.3%
Wasting	276	54.7%
Both Stunting & Wasting	320	63.4%

Table 3: Associated Factor and its Significance to Nutritional Outcome

Factor (N=505)	Details	Nutritional status		Chi-square	P -value
		Undernutrition	Normal nutrition	266.145	< 0.0001
Education of the mother/caretaker	Illiterate	154 (30.5%)	4 (0.8%)		
	Literate	72 (14.3%)	275 (54.5%)		

Discussion

The prevalence of under-nutrition was found to be 63.4%, and that of only stunting and wasting was found to be 53.3% and 54.7% respectively. The results suggest that the proportions of underweight stunting and wasting are much higher in this study population. This study established that children with stunting, wasting and underweight are more likely to come from households where the primary caretaker is not well-educated and aware of good hygiene and sanitation practices. This study endorses that poverty and inaccess to the necessities of life could be linked with under-nutrition in most developing nations like India. Poverty and food insecurity are closely related because poverty can affect social health and create disadvantages that people experience. [7] Food is a major household expense for poor families, and many poor families still face food insecurity due to scarcity, instability, and variable income. This study also attempts to analyse the association of under-nutrition with oral diseases. Under-nutrition is prone to oral diseases such as dental caries and periodontal diseases, and conversely, poor oral health can lead to under-nutrition, influenced by socio-demographic characteristics. Under-nutrition can affect the body's homeostasis, so that it can indirectly lead to the development of oral diseases by reducing resistance to microbial biofilms and reducing tissue healing ability. [8] In this study, the prevalence of dental caries in children was found to be 37.6%. Cavities that are not treated will cause them to expand and deepen, so they will press the nerves that cause a toothache. Necessary action is required to improve the oral hygiene and nutritional status of the most vulnerable household children of the community. [9] Also, teachers, parents and mid-day meal programme managers & administrators must consider the above factors while planning for corrective steps to improve the nutritional status of school children. Political support seems to have a greater impact on it. So, all necessary steps are essential for making an appropriate policy towards the reduction of malnutrition. Continuous collection of

information is necessary to see whether improvement is taking place or not over the successive years, particularly in the underprivileged community. Periodic deworming, provision of iron, folic acid, etc, need to be ensured. Intersectoral collaboration is required to control under-nutrition in the community through the services of Anganwadi Centres. Children should have awareness of oral health issues, which will have a positive impact on their physical health. There should be oral health education included in the school-level curriculum. There should be adequate posting of infographics/posters on oral health in the classroom for the students. The students should be sensitised to the effects of bad eating habits of snacks, as the consumption of large amounts of snacks contributes to oral diseases in children. There should be a follow-up study to physically examine the oral health of the students for the prevalence of caries, gingivitis, and other possible oral diseases in children. This seems to be useful as a long-term measure within the community.

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Declaration of competing interests

No conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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